

**Monitoring Compliance with Kenya’s Shisha Ban
in select public hospitality venues in Nairobi**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction

Seven countries in the WHO African Region have banned the sale and/or use of shisha. In 2017, Kenya implemented a comprehensive ban on shisha, including the use, import, manufacture, sale, offer of sale, advertising, promotion, distribution, and encouraging or facilitating its use. The objective of this study was to assess compliance with the ban of shisha use in select public hospitality venues in Nairobi, Kenya.

Methods

Observational study that used a purposive sampling to select restaurants, bars, and nightclubs where shisha use took place before the ban. A total of 200 venues were visited in seven areas of Nairobi City County, Kenya. Shisha use was defined as at least one person smoking shisha in any indoor or outdoor area of the venue accessible to the public, and indicators of shisha use, as the display of any shisha equipment.

Results

Overall, 81.5% of the venues visited were in compliance. Shisha smoking was observed in 16.5% of all venues and shisha equipment alone was observed in 2.0%. Among the different venue types, 94.6% of restaurants were compliant, 79.7% of bars, and 75.6% of nightclubs.

Discussion

The overall high compliance indicates that Kenya's shisha ban is well implemented in Nairobi, and may be explained by the comprehensive nature of the shisha ban and the low prevalence in the general population. The variation in compliance may be due to the higher rates of use in university students and the additional resources required to enforce the ban in areas with high rates of crime.

What this paper adds

- There is no research that has examined comprehensive bans on shisha consumption. To the authors' best knowledge, this is the first study to assess compliance with a shisha ban law, not only in the WHO African Region but in the world.
- This study found that overall, there is high compliance with the ban on shisha use in hospitality venues in select areas in Nairobi, Kenya more than a year after its implementation.

INTRODUCTION

Shisha, like all forms of smoked tobacco, is addictive and harmful to the user and nearby non-users.¹ Globally, its popularity has increased and expanded globally, especially among youth.² In the World Health Organization (WHO) African Region (AFRO), youth prevalence (current shisha smoking of students age 13-15) ranges from 18.2% in Mauritania³, 11.6% in Djibouti,⁴ 6.5% in Sierra Leone,⁵ 5.4% in Kenya,⁶ 4.6% in Senegal,⁷ 2.4% in Gabon,⁸ 1.7% in Uganda,⁹ to 1.3% in Ghana.¹⁰ Adult prevalence (current shisha smoking of adults age 15 or older) is lower than youth use: 0.3% in Ethiopia,¹¹ 0.3% in Nigeria,¹² 0.2% in Botswana,¹³ 0.2% in Tanzania,¹⁴ 0.2% in Uganda,¹⁵ and 0.1% in Cameroon.¹⁶

Since the WHO Framework Convention on Tobacco Control (FCTC) entered into force in 2005, an increasing number of AFRO countries have adopted tobacco control legislation, including seven countries that ban the use and/or sale of shisha: Mauritius (2008), Uganda (2015), Niger (2017), Rwanda (2017), Kenya (2017), Ethiopia (2019), and Senegal (2020).¹⁷ In Kenya, *The Tobacco Control Act, 2007* and *The Tobacco Control Regulations, 2014* regulate smoking in public places, mandate health warning labels on tobacco products, and ban tobacco advertising, promotion, and sponsorship.^{18,19} On December 28, 2017, Kenya adopted and implemented a comprehensive shisha ban. *The Public Health (Control of Shisha Smoking) Rules, 2017* (shisha ban), prohibits the import, manufacture, sale, offer of sale, use, advertising, promotion, distribution, and encouraging or facilitating use of shisha.²⁰

Tobacco control compliance studies from AFRO is limited, including a few smoke-free compliance studies from Uganda²¹, Ethiopia²², Togo²³, and South Africa²⁴ but no studies assessing compliance with the ban of shisha use. The objective of this study was to examine compliance with the provision of Kenya's shisha ban that prohibits its use in select public hospitality venues in Nairobi, Kenya. To our knowledge this is the first study to assess compliance with a shisha ban, not only in AFRO but in the world.

METHODS

This was an observational study that used a purposive sampling method based on venue type and density to select public places where shisha was primarily consumed prior to the

ban.^{25,26} A total of 200 venues were visited in seven areas of Nairobi City County, Kenya:²⁷ Eastleigh (n= 33), Westlands (n= 36), Parklands (n= 35), Langata (n= 33), Kasarani (n=37), Mathare Valley (n=4), and Pipeline (n=22).

The study areas were selected because they contained a high density of hospitality venues representing different socioeconomic settings: low-income (Mathare Valley, Pipeline), middle-income (Eastleigh, Kasarani), and high-income (Westlands, Parklands). Initially, Mathare Valley and Pipeline were considered separate areas for data collection, however, data collection was suspended in both areas for security reasons and their data was combined. Data collection was carried out from May to June 2019, between seventeen and eighteen months after the ban was implemented

Trained data collectors worked in pairs to follow the sampling protocol: start at a pre-selected starting point and visit every open restaurant, bar, and nightclub on that street, then those on the immediate opposite street, then the immediate perpendicular streets until an approximately similar number of venues were visited in each study area. Venues were visited when shisha use was most likely to occur: from 19:00 to 2:00 on Fridays, Saturdays, and Sundays. Each venue was observed for 15 minutes or until shisha use or indicators of shisha use were observed, whichever happened first. The average observation time was 15.58 minutes/venue. Observations were made discreetly; data collectors did not inform venue employees about the study. Data collectors completed a structured questionnaire adapted from *Assessing Compliance with Smoke-Free Laws*²⁸ on the mobile survey application *Magpi* (Supplemental material 1).

Shisha use was defined as at least one person smoking shisha in any indoor or outdoor area of the venue accessible to the public. Indicators of shisha use was defined as the display of any shisha equipment, including a complete shisha instrument, bowls, and pipes, in any publicly accessible area. A venue was considered compliant if neither shisha smoking nor shisha equipment were observed.

Ethics approval was not sought because it was an observation study in which no personal information was collected and the data collectors' interaction with other people was limited to ordering food or drink if necessary.

RESULTS

The sample consisted of 59.0% (n=118) bars, 22.5% (n=45) nightclubs, and 18.5% (n=37) restaurants. Overall, 81.5% (n= 163) of the venues visited were in compliance (Table 1).

Table 1 Compliance with shisha ban by area and venue type in Nairobi City County (May-June, 2019)

Area	Compliance with shisha ban	
	n	%
Westlands	36	100.0
Kasarani	36	97.3
Eastleigh	29	87.9
Langata	25	75.8
Mathare Valley and Pipeline	17	65.4
Parklands	20	57.1
TOTAL	163	81.5
Venue Type		
Restaurant	35	94.6
Bar	94	79.7
Night club	34	75.6
TOTAL	163	81.5

Shisha smoking was observed in 16.5% (n=33) of all venues and shisha equipment alone was observed in 2% (n= 4).

DISCUSSION

Our findings suggest that while overall there was a high level of compliance, there was significant variation by area and to a lesser degree by venue type. The high compliance may be

due in part to the ban's comprehensiveness as it prohibits other facets that impact its use, including marketing and promotion. It aligns with the high compliance to Kenya's comprehensive TAP ban, and may explain why compliance to Kenya's partial smoking ban (designated smoking areas are permitted) is much lower.^{29,30} This is in keeping with global evidence that compliance is higher to comprehensive tobacco control laws compared to partial, non-FCTC compliant laws.^{31,32, 33}

The high compliance may also reflect the low prevalence of shisha use in the general population. However, the variation in compliance, specifically the areas and venues with lower compliance, may be where young people, particularly university students, go out and consume shisha as shisha use in this population appears to be much higher compared to the general population.^{34,35}

It is unlikely that high compliance is due to strong enforcement,³⁶ however, the variation in compliance could be impacted by enforcement. For example, Mathare Valley is in an area with high rates of crime^{37,38} and enforcement officers may require additional resources, such as police protection, that hamper enforcement more so than other safer areas.

These findings suggest that a comprehensive shisha ban could be an effective policy measure to reduce and prevent shisha consumption. Further research is needed to better understand its impacts, such as changes in prevalence, perceptions of risk, and product availability and whether compliance differs in contexts where shisha use is higher and more culturally engrained.

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Competing interests None declared.

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